

Cyber Security in Current Era in Pakistan: An Analysis of Cyber-Crimes and Cyber-Laws of Pakistan

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Abstract

The study discussed the cyber laws in Pakistan and how these laws are preventing cyber-crimes and how much these laws are up to date along with this the study also studied the legality of pirated softwares in Pakistan and internationally. Two research objectives were focused about the pirated softwares and the cyber laws of Pakistan. The study was a systematic review in which 25 articles from journals along with PECA 2016, electronic transition ordinance 2002 and cyber laws dragged in 2007 were reviewed to know the legality of pirated softwares and how these pirated softwares were treated around the globe. Concluded that there was made of laws related to cyber-crimes and up to date technologies in order to cope with the cyber-crimes that were conducted by the use of these modern devices so that the cybercriminals could be arrested and can be punished. All this should be done in order to protect the identity and privacy of the people who are using these technologies. The study concluded that there is a requirement for new laws which are up to date so that these laws can protect the country and its people and their online life so that their privacy and identity cannot be stolen.

Keywords: Cyber Security, Cyber Laws, Cybercrimes, Pirated Softwares, Cyber Criminals

Introduction

The use of computer as an instrument for committing a crime or to perform any illegal activity in general term is known as cyber-crime. The activities like committing of fraud, stealing of intellectual property and identity along with the violation of privacy are the major crimes that can be committed by the use of computer as an instrument. Cyber-crime has grown over the period of time because the importance of computer has also become central in the fields of commerce, entertainment, education and other related fields and it also has become important for governments to run their countries. The involvement of Americans in most of the cyber-crimes is due to the fact that America has adopted the technology of computer earlier than any other nation and Internet also became available to anyone in public for public use in America than any other nation which led to believe that most of the Americans were involved in cyber-crimes. This is also the reason do too which most of the early victims of cyber-crimes for Americans as they were exploited by cybercriminals in early days of computer revolution when security of the computers was not very strong and

was easily vulnerable. In 21st century there is hardly any discipline which is not being affected by cyber-crimes because computer has become almost essential part of every field of life which can be either education or controlling a government. With the advent of technologies new crimes have also been invented which includes cyber-crimes which are the latest and new type of crimes spreading all around the globe. Cyber-crime involving Internet is representing an extension off already existed criminal behavior along with some novel and new ideas about illegal activities as cyber-crimes most of the times involve young generation which are very much knowledgeable about computer technology.

In cyber-crimes like that do not take place on human body as there is no physical involvement of humans in cyber world but the attacks take place on personal or corporate virtual body which are totally dependent on modern technological changes do to which informational qualities that describe people and institutes on internet are being harmed because of these cyber-crimes. In other words, it can be said that in the modern digital phase our visual individualities are very important in our day-to-day life because in the world of computer we are just a pack of numbers add identifiers in computer records owned by different managements and organizations due to which our digital identity is very important in this current age. Cyber-crimes enlighten the importance of computer networks in our daily routine and also and entails that fragility off such facts as individual identity. The Internet has spread around the globe due to which the criminals off Internet have a lot of walloping places in the real world and in the world of network because of the availability of many hacking tools along with virtual networks so it is very difficult and time-consuming to catch these criminals.

Catching cybercriminals is very much like catching criminals in in daily life as in physical world good evening as can be followed because they usually leave marks behind them in the form of clues that a skilled detective can followed same is the case with the cyber world in which cybercriminals usually leave clues show that their identity and location can be tracked and they can be caught disdain their best energies to concealment their trail. To cope with this in 1996 the Council of Europe collectively with government representatives from United States, Canada and Japan drafted an international treaty which is preliminary in its status so that thus crimes related to cyber world can be covered and criminals can be arrested. Immediately after this treaty international liberation groups immediately started protesting as there was a provision in this pretty that Internet service providers would store data and information regarding customers and their transactions and could hand over this information to government on demand.

Cybercrimes also involves the use of pirated software as pirated softwares are the softwares which are copied without proper copyright and permission from the founder of the software and the reason for using these softwares is the extremely expensive nature of original softwares and many students and researchers related to the field of academia find themselves in tough situation because of these high costs and instead of purchasing them they start using pirated softwares. Students might need an expensive and highly specialized software for their study in a particular aspect or field of education so that they can progress with their research project but due to very high cost and limited budget they find themselves difficult or impossible in allocating enough money for the purchase of the product so they

move towards the use of pirated softwares. Pirated softwares could be any software that can be used without the permissions provided by the manufacturer or distributor and it is mainly a cheap or illegal copies of the version and usually entailed by using their title cracked software which someone intentionally modified so that it can behave in the intended way that it is supposed to behave.

Statement of Problem

The problem to be addressed in this research is the grant situation of cyber security in this modern era in Pakistan and how the cyber laws are being updated in order to cope with modern cyber-crimes. Due to the advent in technology the crimes have also been evolved which have now been shifted from physical crimes to cyber-crimes in which no human being is physically assaulted but his virtual identity is being damaged because of these crimes so in order to track these criminals and to punish them cyber professionals and updated cyber laws are required respectively.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this research is to study the cyber-crimes and their advancement in Pakistan over the period add to understand how cyber laws have evolved in order to cope with these cyber-crimes. As in the advancement of technology the crimes have also been involved and now in the current era physical assault crimes have very much been replaced by cyber-crimes and in order to cop these crimes cyber professionals and updated cyber laws are required. This study will focus on the current cyber laws and they require advancements.

Research Objectives

The objectives of this research are following:

1. To see the legality of pirated softwares in Pakistan in comparison to international status.
2. To see the evolvment of cyber laws and also the scope of current cyber laws.

Research Questions

The study will be based on following research questions:

1. What is the legality of using pirated softwares in Pakistan and internationally?
2. How much cyber-crimes have evolved in Pakistan and are the laws of Pakistan also evolved likewise?

Significance of research

The main thing that inspired me to do this research is to inform and contribute to the knowledge that is developing in the field of cyber law. This research is a tool for building knowledge and increasing understanding and is a mean to understand cyber-crimes in Pakistan. It is also a mean to observe people's understanding of cyber laws and crimes. A famous line by Hudson Maxim; "All progress is born of inquiry. Doubt is often better than over confidence, for it leads to inquiry and inquiry leads to invention." By this we can

understand the significance of research. In addition to above, the significance of research is for students it will be a mean to get help and for professionals it will mean a source of improvement if usage was a bit different and is also for philosophers it will give them new ideas and ways of thinking.

The research will highlight the importance of cyber laws in order to cope with cyber-crimes of the current age. The research will also highlight the need of any changes in current laws and also about the school and legality of pirated softwares and how the use of these softwares can be made legal or can overcome force that the legal softwares with proper permission can be used by different fields which are dependent on computers for their day-to-day work.

Literature Review

Cyber-crimes originated due to the dependency on computers and the shifting of life towards online. Computer is considered one of the utmost discoveries of modern century and it has totally evolved the life of everyone. It is one of the utmost creations of 20th century which has revolutionized the world. Nowadays every field of life is dependent on computers like the field of engineering use computers to simulate their designs of buildings so that they can plan the whole building beforehand and then implement that plan accordingly with the application of every physics law which they required to implement in the construction of that building and this can save a lot of money. On the other hand, business transactions banking everything has shifted online which enabled people to shop from their home and to pay money through online transactions instead of using paper money beside this education has also shifted online and the demonstration of which was given during the COVID-19 pandemic which has revolutionized the use of computers and mobiles in the world. There are pros of computers but on the other hand there are a lot of palms related to computers which includes cyber-crimes. The physical crimes have been shifted online in which people usually do fraud and blackmail other people by using computers and it is a bit easy because the trail of these crimes is very difficult to follow and so it is very difficult to arrest those criminals and it requires a lot of effort and money to arrest these criminals.

Digital Technologies and Society

With the acceptance of digital technologies at a broader level many societies have shifted towards online from spending with communal interactions and even the business industry has also been shifted online but on the contrary side crimes have also been shifted online. It is being reported in the latest reports that cyber-crimes are showing an increasing trend not only in frequency but also in severity (“Hiscox Cyber Readiness Report 2019,” 2019) as it were observed that the cyber-crime has climbed from \$3 trillion in 2015 to \$6 trillion in 2021 and the most highlighting fact is that these numbers have gone far more ahead than traditional crimes in numbers and even in cost (Anderson et al., 2019).

In the cyber security chain individuals are still the feeblest connection in the whole chain and as that time passes cyber criminals are working faster 10 the users or professionals whose job is to prevent cyber-crimes. In other words it can be concluded that there is a miss balance between defending activities and possible attacks because in the process attackers

are more advanced than the defenders (Sardar & Wahsheh, 2020). In this study the researchers focused on investigating the effective measures that can prevent and help users to stay secure and to prevent any vulnerability to the cyber-attacks. The program designed in this study was not limited to a specific major cyber-attack but it provided help related two different types of cyber-crimes and drug classification as the program consisted of hands-on exercises because these can attract the participation of people along with material provided to them for reading. Furthermore, a game dubbed name that attack was used by the participants so that they can give a scenario and they have to name the cyber-attack being used in that particular scenario along with this in on the next day the participants were sent emails to see that if they can be a victim to that specific cyber-attack or not after receiving so much explanation and presentation about cyber-attacks so that the behavior of participants and their information or knowledge can be understood.

A study was conducted on cyber security and farmers of the United States and other people related to agriculture industry were made part of this study and it was found during the study that more than half of the respondents had been victims of cyber-crimes in different forms (Geil et al., 2018). The study was aimed to survey the farmers and other people related to agriculture business about their thinking related to cyber security and the determination of this research was also to find how is education and gender can affect the perception of people about cyber security and cyber-crimes. Health confidence model was used as a agenda and the survey measured how people perceive about harshness, benefits, barricades and self-efficacy. It was concluded from the survey that the attitude and susceptibility towards cyber-attacks as the benefits of protective technology depends on individual's choice to implement cyber security technology which on the other hand means that perception about cyber-attacks and cyber security depends on the perceived ability of a person as how he viewed this threat.

Cyber-Security and Muslim Law

Muslim countries where Sharia law is adopted have also adopted laws to prevent cyber-crime (Hasanah, 2018). In this study Muslim countries where Sharia law is implemented were made the part of the research and it was observed that how these Muslim countries are dealing with cyber-crimes as these are the crimes which came into existence in the modern world where technology is ruling every field of life. The researcher observed Saudi Arabia United Arab Emirates and other countries where Sharia law is implemented. It was found by the researcher that these countries have implemented Sharia law in such a way that it can but also against cyber-crimes as if the cyber-crime is related to tap then that Sharia law punishment which is about cutting the hand will be given and if in some case audio to some reason the cyber-crime caused someone's death then death penalty will be awarded to the person due to which the other person died because of the cyber-crime. So, it can be concluded that these countries have implemented laws against cyber-crime in such a way that these considered cyber-crimes as likely to be physical crimes but conducted by the use of computers which means that there is no distinction between cyber-crime and physical crime in these countries but only the way these were committed.

Cyber-Crimes at Global Level

A global survey was done by Norton cyber safety about cyber-crimes and cyber safety and cyber security around the world and this study showed very different results from the study being conducted in 2019 and showed an increase in cyber security threats over the years (Symantec Corporation, 2019). It was observed in the study that nearly every two individuals among the three were spending more time on Internet then before and they also emphasize that they have taken precautions more than before online because of the concerns related to cyber-crime. It was also observed during the study that the people of United States and India are taking more precautions and taking precautions more seriously than those people belonging to Japan. Furthermore about 50% of the adults are more worried about being the victims of cyber-crime but the same proportion didn't know how they should protect themselves when they suffer from cyber-crime. The study found that the adults in Japan are worried more about cyber-crimes and feel themselves insecure two cyber-crimes after the pandemic and most of them even don't know how to protect themselves from these cyber-crimes. During the past 12 months about 330 million people became the victim of cyber-crimes and from 2019 overall more than 475 million consumers suffered from this crime. The research was conducted online by the Harris poll on behalf of Norton and for this study 10,030 adults were made part of the survey. Different proportion of adults were taken from different countries and different majors were used so that different variables can be accounted for. People have also taken steps to protect themselves from cyber-crimes and for this they mostly use passwords which are stronger and also limit their information on social media so that people can't intrigue their personal life.

Cyber Threats and Ethics

Cyber threats ranging from misconduct or war are very assorted and their patterns are not easy to draft and it is very difficult to find that trail of these crimes (Guinchard, 2011). It has been observed that there are a lot of complexities in the collection and collaboration of data related to cyber-crime for that the proper trail can be found. There is physical exposure of cyber risks to physical premises and softwares which are important element of cyber-crime hand in this aspect software should be given particular attention. Many of the crimes that fall under cyber-crime extremism and war mostly exploit the weakness in the fundamental technology and to benefit from this weakness in the technology. The reason for such vulnerabilities is that these vulnerabilities themselves are not considered to be illegal because these are the bugs in the software and they are overlooked in that debate on cybersecurity. It has been observed by the writer in the studies that the costs had been measured and combined in the cost of cyber-crime and the analysis exposed that cyber-crime is not mattered much but these vulnerabilities unleashed a range of possibilities by which anyone can exploit anyone at any time and can damage their reputation. The threats related to cyber-crime are showing increasing trend over the years therefore it is required to re assess the risk for these cyber-crimes and to reassess the security required to overcome these crimes and to prevent vulnerabilities because of these cyber-crimes.

A universalistic discourse ethics can be very beneficial and can play the basis for cyber ethics (Mbinjama-Gamatham & Olivier, 2020). Habermans's discourse ethics and the ability of communicative action indicates that for a world full of multi cultures and linguistic communication are universal discourse ethics it is a very important step for ensuring cyber

ethics. Search it discuss the role of technology send deepfakes and discussed it by using terminology known as dark technology in which the researcher explained the creation of fake porn in the form of deepfake videotapes which are being used to degrade and destroy the reputation of others individual space of internet and these actions are very difficult to tackle. This led to many problems for the celebrities especially related to their privacy which imposes a serious ethical question on cyber technology. This led to think about the question that what the foundation of human violation and action is; is it nature or is it culture which in other sense is also known as nurture. Is that a subject discussed that after getting information about those who hurt others by using of cyber technology there is a need to develop cyber ethics so that these can be implemented in order to prevent people from cyber-crimes.

Cyber-crimes committed by someone usually appeared to gain leadership structure and to get specialization and make their name (Broadhurst et al., 2014). The study discussed the nature of groups and people involved in cyber-crimes and also enlightens the definition and scope of cyber-crime. The study also highlights empirical and theoretical challenges that are being required to address cyber-crimes and also explain about cyber offenders and their role as most of them are organized in the form of groups. The paper also highlights some examples about non cases that presents the information about individual and group behavior and how they are motivated to be cyber offenders. It is believed that different organizational structures are being involved in cyber-crimes and most of these cyber-crimes are conducted at state level in order to harm another state and ark committed in an organized way in which some kind of enterprise or profit-oriented activity was involved because it was observed that most of the time the activities which are tend to be but her best activities are less organized and have weak chain of command due to which day can't have a solid impact.

Less money should be spent on the anticipation of cyber-crimes and instead of doing this money should be spent in response to cyber-crime which involves hunting down cyber criminals and throwing them in jail and awarding them severe punishments so there this project business of cyber-crime can be lowered (Anderson et al., 2019). This study was believed to be the initial systematic study of the costs related to cyber-crimes and the paper was prepared because of a request from the United Kingdom ministry of defence because they were often viewed that previous studies had hyped the problem related to cyber-crimes and this paper highlighted the direct and indirect cost along with the cost for defence against cyber-crimes. The study distinguish between traditional crimes that now are being conducted online and are now being referred as cyber-crimes which includes tax and welfare fraud and these crimes have been changed substantially because of their shift towards online such as fraud related to money has now been shifted towards credit card fraud and new crimes now came into existence because of the internet as it is being served as a platform for these crimes and the cybercriminals are using Internet for their advantage to extract money from the victims. It was observed in the study that due to the shifting of these crimes online the indirect cost and defence cost has become much higher for these cyber-crimes than stop cost allocated to tackle with traditional crimes and the example of which is that in 2010\$2.7 million were recovered by spending 1/3 of this but for cyber-crimes this is not the case as this amount as this amount is very inefficient and not sufficient for fighting against

cyber-crimes and the cost related to these crimes is also exponentially higher than traditional crimes do to which these crimes are becoming global because of did online nature. It was concluded in the study that more amount of money should be spent on hurting down cybercriminals and throwing them in jail with severe punishments so that they can be served as an example for others and the prevention of cyber-crimes can be done in a better way instead of spending money on the anticipation of cyber-crimes.

It was also observed by the researcher that if people believe and have positive attitude towards software piracy then they have more intention towards the use of pirated software as they consider it their right to use this because of the fact that they can't afford it and are required to use it (Chen et al., 2009). It was also observed during their search that variables related to morality which include judgment and intensity have negative impacts on the intention of consumers towards the use of pirated software which indicates that consumer on the other side think that the use of these software is not legal.

Cyber World and Recent Development

Despite stop benefits off the Internet of Things in smart applications the security threats are increasing exponentially day by day and is leading to different crimes (Gurunathan et al., 2022). The study highlighted that the Internet of Things has become one of the most actively researched topics is smart appliances that has attracted a lot of attention from developers and researchers. The purpose of Internet of Things is to attach billions of things by sharing and by getting that information with the use of IP which is also known as Internet Protocol dad makes the devices to store and then to access data online at any point of time because the data is stored on an online server but on the other hand security threats are expected to be exponentially high because that data is stored on online servers which can be accessed easily from other computers and then can be hacked or can be breached. The Internet of Things has integrated in our lives and will be more integrated in our lives in future and it is very important to pay attention to cyber threats so that these threats can be overcome and public can't feel safe on internet. The study reviewed the literature of articles published from 2010 to 2019 and observed how Internet of Things was being considered in the literature. Half of the organizations have suffered from cyber-attacks of some kind in the recent past years and these attacks are increasing day by day and are making people to lose confidence in internet ("Hiscox Cyber Readiness Report 2019," 2019).

It has been observed that cyber criminals used proceedings and governmental declarations to sensibly plan and then perform their cyber-crime operations in order to trap people (Lallie et al., 2021). It was observed that during COVID-19 pandemic there was a remarkable increase in cyber-crime because the world has shifted totally towards online platform which provides unique opportunities for cyber criminals to execute cyber-crimes and effect people's social life and business life. During the COVID. The industry that got the most increase was gaming industry and online shopping and people used both of these platforms to spam other peoples and to commit cyber-crimes. The study revealed that when this pandemic started in China the online crimes also started in China and their number started to increase over the period and when this pandemic become global same happened with the cyber-attacks because businesses and social life have shifted towards online do to

which these crimes also have shifted online. It was also observed that cybercriminals took opportunities by utilizing events and government announcements so that they can carefully plan and execute their cyber campaigns.

Research Methodology

Research Design

The study was aimed to determine the legality of pirated softwares in Pakistan and then compare the legality or illegality of these softwares around the globe. The main purpose of this research watch to see that why buy rated softwares are so much abundant in Pakistan and how these softwares are causing threats to cybersecurity. The way to analyse this question and to answer this the researchers observed and did systematic review of web documents articles and newspaper editorials to get information about pirated softwares and the threats related to them in Pakistan and how these softwares were being considered around the globe. The study was also aimed to understand the current situation of cyber laws in Pakistan and how these laws can cope with current cyber-crimes as the cyber-crimes are progressing day by day in a very fast pace and cyber laws on the other hand are very outdated in Pakistan. The research was aimed at to study the deficiencies or challenges being faced by cyber laws in order to implement them according to the given situation and for this the researcher will analyse PECA act 2016 and electronic transaction ordinance 2002 and will observe these according to the required outcomes and laws in the current situation of Pakistan as technology is progressing day by day and stop evolvment of these crimes related to cyber are also developing at a very fast pace.

Research Method

The research is a qualitative and systematic review research as in this research the researcher will review systematically the laws of Pakistan and journals and related research about cyber-crimes and how pirated softwares are being considered by that they are considered legal or illegal and how they are being attached with cyber-crimes.

Population

The population and sample for this study is going to be PECA 2016 and electronic transition ordinance 2002 and cyber laws dragged in 2007. Moreover, articles and journals about cyber-crimes and about pirated software and how these softwares are being considered around the globe and in Pakistan are being considered the part of the research and that surgery will analyse these and will base his research on this.

Sample size

A total of 25 articles were being reviewed and surveyed by the researchers answer the research questions based on the research objectives of this research which are about the legality of pirated softwares in Pakistan and the requirements and changes being required in cyber laws of Pakistan to make them up to date and what challenges and barriers are already being present in these last four Pakistani people.

Results and Discussion

The researcher analyzed different articles related to software piracy (Chen et al., 2009; Liao et al., 2010; Phau & Ng, 2010; Rahman et al., 2022) and observe that all these articles discussed about pirated softwares in a way that people don't want to use these softwares but they are forced due to financial circumstances as they can't afford licenses of or regional product or software. It was also observed by the researcher that if people believe and have positive attitude towards software piracy then they have more intention towards the use of pirated software as they consider it their right to use this because of the fact that they can't afford it and are required to use it (Chen et al., 2009). It was also observed during their search that variables related to morality which include judgment and intensity have negative impacts on the intention of consumers towards the use of pirated software which indicates that consumer on the other side think that the use of these software is not legal.

As for internationally the use of pirated software is concerned there are very strict laws for the violation of software copyright and as a consequence of this individuals or companies whoever violates this copyright can face a penalty of \$150,000 and can also lead up to five years of imprisonment (Partida, n.d.). The strictness of rules related to pirated software can be found from that if someone uses pirated softwares innocently it is like that they are breaking the law and they have to face serious consequences for doing so. But on the other hand if we observe Pakistan we can find that most of the organizations including education institutions are using softwares invited forms and they are not buying their licenses in order to save money yet no action is being taken against them and the reason for this is that these companies are multinational and they have no official representatives in Pakistan because there are laws present in electronic transition ordinance for piracy but no one has brought this issue up or filed a case do to which people are using pirated softwares consistently.

Users can only create copies of a piece of software for backup purpose and can't create any copy of software that requires complete or explicit permission from the copyright holder or from the founder of the software (U.S. Copyright Office, 2016). The reason for so much fine and care about piracy is that computer programs are a part of huge industry and they generate billions of dollars every year because of their importance for revenue and profits that is why their piracy matters a lot as they are a property of the founder so it can't be pirated without proper copyrights. It can also be seen as like stealing someone's work and using it without their permission. The development of software involves years of research add skilful coding then it took a lot of effort to obtain license so that it can be entered into the market that is why proper care in the form of license is provided to the softwares so that they can't be pirated. Strict penalties are given to the people who pirated softwares as it was already discussed that cyber-crimes are also being treated as physical crimes conducted through the use of computers that is why strong punishments are awarded to the criminals. The other reason for the awarding strict punishments is that it is very difficult to find the trail of the crime and it requires a lot more effort and money to arrest the criminal that is why the fine and penalty for these criminals is very severe so that they can be made a model for others in order to prevent cyber-crimes around the world. Almost all countries have laws especially related to cyber-crimes and they are far more updated after

the COVID-19 pandemic but unfortunately in Pakistan these laws are very outdated and were updated in 2016 but they don't cover cyber-crimes in such a manner that they should cover. Pakistan is lagging behind in modern technology due to its economic and financial situation and is facing cyber threats whereas the world has shifted online and is working day and night to improve their online security so that they can make their people safe in this digital world and can prevent the access of other countries to the information of their people so that they can feel secure and can't be harmed in any way during critical times.

As for the laws related to pirated softwares there are no such laws in Pakistan and cyber laws of Pakistan are very limited and surround around 24 to 25 aspects. Most of these aspects cover online frauds, cyber stalking, cyber spoofing, online harassment and other crimes like promoting the offences online. The laws of Pakistan are silent regarding pirated softwares or other softwares or computer operating systems because there is need of a lot of advancement in Pakistan regarding the understanding of operating systems and legality of softwares. The reason for the use of softwares which are pirated in educational institutes and government institutes is only due to the fact there is no law regarding these softwares and there is a dire need of time to do legislations to cover this aspect so that the software programmers who want to develop their own softwares can be acclaimed. The reasons for less development of softwares in Pakistan is the unavailability of laws as there are no laws which provide security to the software because if the softwares are not being prevented from being pirated then why people will waste their time on producing such softwares when they can't even earn money from it by selling the license office that is why most of the software engineers of Pakistan usually work abroad on big projects instead of working in Pakistan.

In Pakistan to cope with cyber-crimes three different statues had been made which one electronic transaction ordinance 2002, electronic cyber-crime bill 2007 and prevention of electronic crimes act 2016 but the problem with these laws is that these are outdated. The first reason for considering these laws as outdated is that revolution in the field of technology which during the COVID-19 pandemic but these laws has not been revised since then and are coping with offenses that were present before the pandemic. As far electronic transaction ordinance 2002 is concerned it is very outdated because in this act electronic documentation was not given any recognition along with electronic records. The other criticism on this ordinance was that it failed to recognize the electronic signatures and transactions along with the lack of recognition of electronic data and forensic evidence. Some of the offences and their punishment mentioned in electronic transaction ordinance 2002 are following:

Table 1. Offences and punishments in electronic transaction ordinance 2002

Offence	Imprisonment (Years)	Fine (Rs.)
False information	7	10,000,000
False certificate	7	10,000,000
Privacy violation	7	1,000,000

Information system damage	7	1,000,000
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In electronic/cyber-crime bill 2007 changes were made in the laws related to cyber-crimes and punishments were also made sweet. This bill end campus is 21 different offenses with punishments ranging from six months to lifetime imprisonment and a fine of 50,000 to 10 million for committing these offences. On the contrary side it is the main criticism on cyber-crime bill 2007 that it only covers 21 cyber issues and is lagging behind to cover all the aspects of new and modern digital era. The problem with this bill was that there were new terms coined by the government by the government in this bill related to cyber-crimes and these words caused more ambiguity in the law for example the word “terroristic” was added in the bill which itself is an imaginary word and has very vague meanings. The other problem with this bill was that instead of giving privacy rights to the people and protecting their privacy rights this bill gave unrestricted controls to federal investigation agency in which this agency can infiltrate anyone’s private space on internet or can conceal anyone’s mobile phone, laptops or any electric gadgets which they feel have doubtful behavior so instead of protecting people’s private life this bill clearly destroyed privacy of the people on internet. Some of the offences and their punishment described in electronic crime bill 2007 are following:

Table 2. Offences and punishments in electronic crime bill 2007

Crime	Captivity (Years)	Fine (Rs.)
Criminal Admittance	3	300,000
Criminal Data Admittance	3	300,000
Data Harm	3	300,000
System Harm	3	300,000
Electronic Deception	7	700,000
Electronic Phoney	7	700,000
Misappropriation of Device	3	300,000
Unofficial access to code	3	300,000
Spiteful code	5	500,000
Insult	5	500,000
Virtual stalking	3	300,000
Virtual spamming	6 months	50,000
Spoofing	3	300,000
Pornography	10	-----
Cyber extremism	Life	10,000,000

The prevention of electronic crimes act 2016 also covered 24 pack and these aspects were mostly covered in cyber-crime bill 2007. There is very less things that were added in this pack to cope with cyber-crimes you know we had no information regarding the use of pirated softwares. The main issue with the sidebar off Pakistan is dead they were very limited and are not able to cope with modern technology and lag far behind in providing cyber security to the inhabitants of Pakistan. When prevention of electronic crimes act was introduced, it compromised multiple constitutional rights of the public of Pakistan which includes freedom of speech. When this act was presented in parliament and public was introduced with the

draft which was poorly lased and was impetuous and full of vagueness. It can also be said that due to the advancement in cyber-crimes these acts of Pakistan need to be upgraded to meet modern standards. It has been observed that no rules no regulations were made and implement regarding the use of pirated softwares in Pakistan and many governmental institutions along with private institutions are using pirated softwares because of the economic and financial conditions of their institutes and it is not being considered illegal to use these types of softwares in Pakistan. The laws of Pakistan are limited to online fraud, spamming, spoofing and the stealing of codes to make a new software which resembles the original software a lot. There is no disagreement in the fact that there is a dire need for up-to-date cyber laws because of the astonishing growth in the field of computers do too which crimes also begin to evolve and in order to cope with these crimes the cyber laws should also be up to date with modern requirements. Some of the offenses and their punishment mentioned in prevention of electronic crimes act 2016 are following:

Table 3: Offences and punishments in electronic crimes act 2016

Offence	Imprisonment (Years)	Fine (Rs.)
Unofficial access to information system or data	3 months	50,000
Unofficial copying or transmission of data	6 months	100,000
Meddling with information system or data	2	500,000
Unofficial access to critical infrastructure information system or data	3	1,000,000
Unofficial copying of critical infrastructure data	5	5,000,000
Meddling with critical infrastructure information system or data	7	10,000,000
Adoration of an offense	7	10,000,000
Cyber terrorism	14	50,000,000
Hatred speech	7	----
Employment funding and planning of terrorism	7	----
Electric forgery	3-7	250,000-5,000,000
Electronic fraud	2	10,000,000
Creation/procurement/delivering device for use in offence	6 months	50,000
Unofficial use of identity information	3	5,000,000
Unauthorized issuance of sim cards	3	500,000

Tempering of communication equipment	3	1,000,000
Unauthorized interception	2	500,000
Offences against dignity of natural person	3	1,000,000
Offense against modesty of natural percent and minor	5 7	5,000,000 5,000,000
Child pornography	7	5,000,000
Malicious code	2	1,000,000
Cyber stalking	3	1,000,000
minor	5	10,000,000
Spamming	3 months	50,000-5,000,000
Spoofing	3	500,000

These were the offenses discussed in cyber laws of Pakistan and these offenses yet up to date but on the other hand are outdated because these do not cope with modern technologies which have totally evolved the world especially after COVID-19 pandemic as everything has been shifted towards online even from grocery shopping two the shopping of cars and their parts. In Pakistan an incident happened in which a man named Taimoor Raza was punished to death for the blasphemy of prophet on Facebook (*Pakistan: Man Sentenced to Death for Blasphemy on Facebook | Pakistan | The Guardian*, n.d.). The antiterrorism court considered this crime they point to that physical crime as blasphemy was done and it is a severe crime either done physically or online due to which the criminal was sentenced to death. This shows that the need of cyber laws as cyber laws can't prevent cyber-crimes because these crimes are not less or in low profile than physical crimes but have their own place in the society and needs to be addressed so that the privacy and information of people can be saved and their views and religious beliefs can be protected.

Conclusion

The study was a systematic study that dealt with the perceptions about pirated software around the globe and how these softwares were being treated in Pakistan. The study did a systematic review of articles newspaper editorials and related material to explore about the legality of pirated softwares and to find why these softwares are being given more importance in the current world and how computer has become such a large industry that even the software's of them have to be purchased fulfilling license requirements. In the next phase the study analyzed the cyber laws in Pakistan and discuss how these laws are playing a role in preventing cyber-crimes and why these laws are outdated and need to be updated so that cyber-crimes can be prevented and controlled in this modern world in order to protect people and their security.

Software license are being given a lot of importance because of the capitalist theory and because of Marxism as these theories state that every business is done in order to gain profit (Øversveen, 2021). The function of private business is just to make profit so in order to make profit and develop their business these softwares which are the product of the businesses are sold in order to gain money. The cyber-crime laws in Pakistan for passed by

a lot of struggle in the parliament and most of the parties don't want to pass these laws as they thought these were not important for the country (Aziz, 2018). The study concluded that there is a requirement for new laws which are up to date so that these laws can protect the country and its people and their online life so that their privacy and identity cannot be stolen. The United States of America banned TikTok as they thought that China can take their data from America and then store it in China (Ahmed et al., 2020). In order to protect the data America banned TikTok and asked China that they should made servers in America where data of Americans can be stored and it will not be taken away from the country. In short it can become noted that in the modern world where technology has become a necessary part of every field of life the laws related to technology are very important and are required to be updated on daily basis as technology is progressing on day-to-day basis so in order to cope with the progress in technology and to prevent crimes which can be committed by the use of this technology. The cyber laws should be strong enough to prevent these crimes and technologies should be provided to these people so that they can prevent cyber-crimes and can follow the trail of those criminals in order to arrest them and to punish them for committing these crimes.

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